

SOCIAL AND EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS OF NEW EDUCATION POLICY OF 2020

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INTRODUCTION:

Education is fundamental for achieving full human potential, developing an equitable and promoting society for national development. Universal high quality education is the best way forward for developing and maximising our country's rich talents and resources for the good of the individual, the society, the country and the world.

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India will have the highest population of young people in the world over the next decade, and our ability to provide high quality educational opportunities to them will determine the future of our country.

Indeed with the quickly changing employment, landscape and global ecosystem it is becoming increasingly critical that children not only learn, but more importantly learn how to learn.

Education thus, must move towards less content and more towards learning about how to think critically and solve problems, how to be creative and multi-disciplinary, and how to innovate, an adapt and absorb new material in novel and changing field.

Education must build character; enable learners to be ethical, rational, compassionate, and caring while at the same time prepare them for gainful, fulfilling employment.

The world is undergoing rapid changes in the knowledge landscape. With various dramatic scientific and technological advances, such as the rise of big data, machine learning, and artificial intelligence, many unskilled jobs worldwide may be taken over by machines, while the need for a skilled workforce, particularly involving mathematics, computer science, and data science, in conjunction with multidisciplinary abilities across the sciences, social sciences, and humanities, will be increasingly in greater demand.

The teacher must be at the centre of the fundamental reforms in the education system. The new education policy must help re-establish teachers, at all levels, as the most respected and essential members of our society, because they truly shape our next generation of citizens. It must do everything to empower teachers and help them to do their job as effectively as possible.

The gap between the current state of learning outcomes and what is required must be bridged through under taking major reforms that bring the highest quality, equity, and integrity into the system, from early childhood care and education through higher education.

This National Education Policy 2020 is the first education policy of the 21st century and aims to address the many growing developmental imperatives of our country. This Policy proposes the revision and revamping of all aspects of the education structure, including its regulation and governance, to create a new system that is aligned with the aspirational goals of 21st century education, including SDG4, while building upon India's traditions and value systems.

The new education policy must help recruit the very best and brightest to enter the teaching profession at all levels, by ensuring livelihood, respect, dignity, and autonomy, while also instilling in the system basic methods of quality control and accountability.

Education Policy lays particular emphasis on the development of the creative potential of each individual. It is based on the principle that education must develop not only cognitive capacities both the “foundational capacities” of literacy and numeracy and ‘higher-order’ cognitive capacities, such as critical thinking and problem solving – but also social, ethical, and emotional capacities and dispositions.

OBEJECTIVES OF THE POLICY:

The main purpose of the education system is to develop good human beings, capable of rational thought and action, possessing compassion and empathy, courage and resilience, scientific temper and creative imagination, with sound ethical moorings and values.

1. Recognizing and fostering unique capabilities of each student by identifying their qualities.
2. Flexibility, so that learners have ability to choose their trajectories end programmes.
3. No hard separations for curricular activities and extracurricular activities between arts and Commerce.
4. Focuses on conceptual learning rather than rote learning and learning for exams.
5. To make more innovative basis it emphasis on creativity and critical thinking.
6. Constitutional values like empathy, respect for others cleanliness, courtesy, spirit of service are more important here.
7. Teachers and faculty as the heart of the learning browse.
8. Extensive use of technology in teaching and learning, removing language barriers, increasing access for divyang students, and educational planning and management;
9. Outstanding research as a co requisite for outstanding education and development;
10. A rootedness and pride in India, and its rich, diverse, ancient and modern culture and knowledge systems and traditions;
11. Life skills such as communication, cooperation, teamwork, and resilience;

VISION OF THE POLICY:

The vision of the policy is to instil among the learners a deep rooted pride in being Indian, not only in thought, but also in spirit, intellect, and deeds, as well as to develop knowledge, skills, values, and dispositions that support responsible commitment to human rights, sustainable development and living, and global wellbeing, thereby reflecting a truly global citizen.

OVERVIEW OF NEW EDUCATION POLICY:

The National Education Policy 2020 which was approved by the union cabinet of India on 29 July 2020. The new policy replaces the previous National Policy on Education, 1986. The main changes and objectives are:

I. LANGUAGES:

The policy raises the importance of mother tongue and regional languages, medium of instruction until class 5 and preferably beyond should be in these languages. Sanskrit and foreign languages will also be given importance into this policy. The policy also states that no language will be imposed on the students.

Shortly after the release of the policy the government clarified that The language policy in national education policy is abroad guideline; and that it was up to the states institutions and schools to decide the implementation more detailed language strategy would be released in the new curriculum framework of 2021.

II. SCHOOL EDUCATION:

The “10+2” structure will be replaced with “5+3+3+4” model. Following stages are included in school education:

Foundational stage:

This is further subdivided into two parts; 3 years of preschool or anganwadi, followed by classes 1 and 2 in primary school. This will cover children of 3 -8 years. The focus of studies will be in activity based learning.

Preparatory stage:

Classes 3 to 5, which will cover the ages of 8 to 11 years. It will gradually introduce subjects like, reading, writing, physical education, languages, art, science and mathematics.

Middle stage:

Classes 6 to 8, covering children between ages 11 and 14. It will introduce students to the more abstract concepts in subjects of mathematics, science, social science, arts and humanities.

Secondary stage:

Classes 9 to 12, covering the ages of 14 to 19 years. It is again subdivided into two parts:

- i. Classes 9 and 10
- ii. Classes 11 and 12

These 4 years of study are intended to inculcate multidisciplinary study, coupled with depth and critical thinking. Multiple options will be provided to students.

Exams:

There are some major changes will apply for exams:

Instead of exams being held every academic year, school students will only attend three exams, in classes 2, 5, and 8. board exams will be continued to be held for classes 10 and 12 but will be re-designed. Standards for this will be formatted by an assessment body, PARAKH (Performance Assessment, Review and Analysis of Knowledge for Holistic Development)

To make it more convenient, these exams would be conducted twice a year, with students being offered up to two attempts. The exams itself would have two parts, namely the objective and descriptive.

Midday meal scheme:

It will be extended to include breakfasts. It mainly emphasis on student's health, particularly mental health, through the deployment of counsellors and social workers.

III. HIGHER EDUCATION:

It proposes a 4 year multi-disciplinary bachelor's degree in an undergraduate programme with multiple exit options. These will include professional and vocational areas and will be implemented as follows:

A certificate after completing one year of study

- A diploma after completing 2 years of study
- A bachelor's degree after completion of a 3 year programme
- A 4 year multidisciplinary bachelor's degree

To regulate higher education some council will be set up some verticals:

- National Higher Education Regulatory Council (NHERC), to regulate higher education, including teacher education, while excluding medical and legal education.
- Higher Education Grants Council (HEGC) for funding and financing of universities and colleges. This will replace the existing National Council for Teacher Education, All India Council for Technical Education and University Grants Commission.
- The National Testing Agency will now be given the additional responsibility of conducting entrance examinations for admissions to universities across the country, in addition to the JEE Main and NEET.
- This policy proposes that higher education institutes like the IITs make changes with regard to the diversity of learning.
- The policy proposes to internationalize education in India. Foreign universities can now set up campuses in India.
- The fees of both private and public universities will be fixed.

IV. TEACHER EDUCATION:

The NEP 2020 puts forward many policy changes when it comes to teachers and teacher education. To become a teacher, a 4 year Bachelor of Education will be the minimum requirement needed by 2030.

The teacher recruitment process will also be strengthened and made transparent. National Curriculum framework for teacher education will be made by National Council for Teacher Education BT 2021.

V. OTHER CHANGES:

- National Education Commission , headed by the Prime Minister of India
- National Research Foundation, to improve research and innovation
- National Educational Technology Forum, a platform to facilitate exchange of ideas on technology usage to improve learning.

- The policy proposes new languages institutions such as the Indian Institute of Translation and interpretation and national institute/institutes for Pali, Persian and Prakrit.

How to successfully implement the New Education Policy?

The new education norms have several upsides, which would prove to be efficient over the old ongoing education policy. There are several ways to implement NEP:

- To implement NEP successfully at all levels, the government will need to create stakeholders incentives so that the implementation is smooth and uniformed.
- Formulate instruments in the form of legal, policy, regulatory and institutional mechanism.
- Build reliable information repositories.
- Develop adaptability across HEIs, regulatory bodies and government agencies.
- Develop creditability through transparent actions and participation of all stakeholders.
- Develop sound principles of management.

CONCLUSION:

The National education policy, which is designed to ease the burden of classroom teaching and examination on students, will play an important role in creating the future of the country .it is success however, lies in uniform and transparent implementation at all levels, with an equitable distribution of resources.

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